

Assessing teachings of the Roman Catholic Church in addressing the ‘second generation’ alcohol abuse in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya

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Published online: 30th August, 2023

Abstract

This paper examines the teachings of the Roman Catholic Church in addressing the “second generation” alcohol abuse in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya. The emerging phenomenon of SGA and its abuse by some RCC believers in Uasin Gishu County necessitated this study. Structural Functional Theory by Emile Durkheim and Symbolic Interaction Theory by George Herbert Mead were used to guide the study. The study targeted the Roman Catholic believers, especially clergy, brewers, addicts, and reformed addicts, rehabilitation counselors and Alcoholic Drinks Control Board members. Purposive sampling technique was used to select 11 informants. Interview Guide and Observation Schedule were used to collect data, which were eventually cleaned and organized. Data was analyzed by discussing information within the context of the study. The following were the key findings of the study: RCC through Pioneer Total Abstinence to Alcohol (PTAA) movement advocates abstinence on all forms of alcohol but some of their teachings and world views of alcohol consumption moderation contradicts in each other. This study concludes that there is a gap, where little is known of SGA (Busaa and Chang’aa) to inform their teachings as comparable to other licit alcohol and therefore recommends the following: the teachings of abstinence by PTAA should be embraced and taught from RCC pulpit; the RCC should have debating engagement with other religious organizations on SGA to inform their teachings; at the policy level, NACADA and county governments should partner with religious organizations among other stakeholders to foster understanding on emerging SGA and substance abuse through National and Regional conferences to build their capacities.

Key words: Teachings, Second Generation Alcohol, Alcohol Abuse.

1. Introduction

Alcohol is the most widely used drug since there are 2 billion alcohol users in the world (Colombo Plan, 2016). The “second generation” alcohol has been adulterated and dangerous for human consumption compared to the normal alcohol and illicit traditional brew. All “second generation” alcohol is killer drinks. With the emergence of precursor chemicals meant for industrial and medical use such as formalin, molasses and after shave, some of these chemicals have been abused to make the “second generation” alcohol (WHO, 2014).

Europe leads the world in alcohol consumption where 73.4% are male drinkers and 59.9% are female drinkers, America comes second with 70.7% male drinkers and 52.8% female drinkers, Africa has 40.2% male drinkers and 19.6% female drinkers with the least being the United Arab Emirates with 7.4% male drinkers and 3.3% female drinkers because of the religious and cultural values (WHO, 2014). In Africa, much of the alcohol consumed is either illegal or home-made (WHO, 2014). This situation poses a risky vulnerability of abusing the “second generation” alcohol in most African countries including Kenya.

Religion, in its teachings, plays an important role in either influencing one into alcoholism or refraining from the same (Gomes, de Andrade, Izbicki, Almeida, & de Oliveira, 2013). Those who attend church services and fellowships tend to shun alcoholism (Regnerus, Smith, & Smith, (2004). The Roman Catholic Church uses wine in their religious observation during Eucharistic celebrations as justified in (Mathew, 26:26-29). This is loaded with a lot of theological and philosophical interpretations which may not be understood by some RCC believers. It poses interpretation challenges especially for the simple and first time visitors attending RCC mass. Some Protestants do not use wine but have substituted it with softer drinks which are not fermented.

2. Statement of the Problem

Increased alcohol consumption in Uasin Gishu County has been exacerbated by the prevalence of the adulterated “second generation” alcohol and some other positions perverted by some RCC believers contrary to the aspiration of RCC. The RCC also appears to be somehow compromised in their articulation of certain theological standpoints which are considered universal. The understanding of alcohol is varied and shrouded with hidden mysteries emanating from place to place. Among many African societies, wine, beer and spirits are considered for the elites due to cost implication and therefore the majority resort to illicit traditional brew which has taken the shape of second generation alcohol. Such exposes

some believers to abuse “second generation” alcohol in Uasin Gishu County. The danger of SGA is its mutation nature of changing faces and names such as “koroga” meaning mixture of chemicals with “busaa” or after shave chemicals mixed with milk. The consumption and abuse of “second generation” alcohol has caused economic, health and social devastation in the society. This paper therefore, examines teachings of the Roman Catholic Church in addressing the “second generation” alcohol abuse in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya.

3. Purpose of the Study

To examine the teachings of the Roman Catholic Church in addressing the “Second Generation” alcohol abuse in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya.

4. Theoretical Framework

Structural-Functionalist Theory (SFT) by Emile Durkheim (1858-1917) according to Van, (2002) was used in the study. The theory helped to explore the functional role of religion in stabilizing society through social institutions. This theory argues that alcohol abuse is a response to the weakening values and norms in society as it undergoes complex social change, (Mooney, Clever, & Van Willigen, 2021). “Second generation” alcohol abuse raises fundamental social disruption by the effects it brings on family and society at large. Concerns to reduce the rate of alcohol abuse should largely be based on societal perspective and relevant engagements to reduce its consumption and devastating effects. Religion comes in with its functional role of teachings to build values and norms in order to address social vices. It is imperative to explore causes of the abuse of alcohol in order to inform prevention strategy, which involves coming up with workable activities. The SFT further assumes that when one part of the society is not functioning well, it can cause dysfunction to the rest of the society leading to disruption of life. As much as this study was majorly concerned with the functional role of religion, it did not leave out the interactions within the phenomena since human beings are social beings by nature. For clearer understanding regarding institutions and its dynamism of interaction, the SFT was supplemented by Symbolic Interaction Theory (SIT) by George Herbert Mead (1934) who was influenced indirectly by Max Weber (Griffin, 2012). The SIT helped in exploring the interaction of human beings as social beings which may create opportunities for possibilities of alcohol abuse.

5. Literature Review

The Pentecostal Assembly of Canada (PAOC) has a strong teaching against the use of alcohol. The stand of the church is that human beings are gifts from God and therefore gifts should be well taken care of. When a gift from God has been turned into a curse, it is the church that must offer an alternative way of life. It is the stand of the church doctrine in Canada that their way of life is to abstain from alcohol. The believers in Canada ardently confess that, “We live in a world with so many good options that enable us to eat, drink and be merry. Therefore alcohol is now becoming an unnecessary commodity with which to enjoy the goodness of God. The commitment to abstain from alcohol is motivated by the desire to be filled with the Holy Spirit (PAOC, 2013).

The Seventh Day Adventist (SDA) church has outlined the effects of alcohol in their teachings and follows this to advise their members to avoid taking alcohol. As much as poverty may appear to grip the rural folk of the members of SDA church, their health would be more devastated if they coupled their poor state with alcohol consumption (Ayiemba, 1992). Further, the foregoing source had identified poor health among the rural believers as among the key contributors of poverty. In their bid to eradicate poor health among the SDA church members, there has been an insistence to totally avoid alcohol.

6. Research Gap

Contemporary Christians as argued by Cook (2006) are in a confused dilemma in understanding where to stand when it comes to alcohol consumption. Such difference in opinion drew the researcher’s attention to investigate much deeper on the teachings of the RCC. This study exposes that there is a gap, where little is known of SGA (*Busaa* and *Chang’aa*) to inform the RCC teachings as comparable to other licit alcohol.

7. Methodology

The study was done in Uasin Gishu County in Kenya. The researcher adopted a philosophical paradigm to select methodology used in the study. The researcher applied social constructivism since the study was qualitative in nature. The qualitative research design used was phenomenology which captured the presenting phenomenon through describing participants experiences (Lester, 1999). The research design gave guidelines towards achieving the desired objectives of the study.

A population of the Roman Catholic believers especially clergy, brewers, addicts and reformed addicts, rehabilitation counselors, administrators, Alcoholic Drinks Control Board (UG ADCB) in Uasin Gishu County was targeted. Purposive sampling was employed to select the participants who have valuable information for the study. Within the context of purposive sampling technique, snowballing was used to identify the right informants. A total of 11 informants were interviewed upon arriving at a point of saturation.

Data was collected using the Interview Guide (IG) and Observation Schedule (OS). The tools were chosen because the study was qualitative in nature. OS was used to collect data from the informants in real-life situations; among the brewers who were found to be going on with their normal activities of brewing and selling the alcohol. Procedure of data collection included: collection of secondary data; pilot study in Nandi County; identifying potential informants and collection of primary data.

Data was cleaned, organized and analyzed. Document Analysis was used to analyze data. Documents that the researcher came across formed part of this. The informants gave their informed consent and voluntarily participated in the study.

8. Findings of the Study

This study came up with the findings which are presented.

8.1 Teachings on Alcohol and Bible Verses which appear controversial and may be used by some RCC Believers to Justify Alcohol

The RCC has teachings on licit alcohol but not SGA second generation alcohol because of its emerging nature. This could be the reason why some informants said that the Roman Catholic Church does not teach its believers on the dangers of “second generation” alcohol abuse (O.I 23/9/2019; O.I 25/9/2019). The Bible records teachings on alcohol in general but not specifically second generation alcohol which is toxic, because it is among the emerging social issues. It can only be compared with what is written in 2 Kings 4:38-40.....*“The stew was poured out for the men, but as they began to eat it, they cried out, “Man of God, there is death in the pot!” And they could not eat it”*. Allegorically, “second generation” alcohol abuse is death in the pot. One informant who is also an addiction counselor confessed that, “second generation” alcohol kills, lowers self-esteem of its victims, retards knowledge and understanding and as well a risk factor in productive health (O.I 16/09/2019).

The findings revealed that there are controversial scriptural texts which believers may abuse to consume alcohol (O. I. 15/09/2019). Our key informant quoted 1Timothy 3:3 where Paul advises Timothy to drink a little wine because of frequent digestion problems which hindered from preaching the gospel. He said some believers and non-believers alike have used this verse to justify their consumption of alcohol leading to addiction. The findings of the current study is in concurrence with the earlier finding of Kituyi (2018) that many RCC members used such Bible verses to justify both preparation and uptake of alcohol (O.I 13/09/2019). This scripture has been quoted out of context because it applied to Timothy who had a condition which may not be the case with everybody else craving for alcoholic drink.

The other controversial verse in the Bible is John 2:1-10 according to our informant (O.I. 15/9/2019). This is when Jesus attended a wedding feast at Cana of Galilee. Mary the mother of Jesus said “And when they ran out of wine, the mother of Jesus said to Him, “They have no wine.” (John 2:3). Eventually Jesus turned water into wine. Some RCC believers have more often used this verse to argue in favor of their drinking habits according to our informants (O. I., 16/09/2019; O.I. 28/09/2019).

Some Catholics cardinally argue that, “If Christ could make wine in the ceremony where He was personally present, then where would one find the guts and audacity to stop them from taking and making alcohol?”(O.I. 22/9/2019). A point of concern which emanates from the foregoing discourse is that the writer of the Bible does not report that people were drunk at Cana. But the “second generation” alcohol makes people drunk, making them get involved in all kinds of nuisance and vices. Given this disparity, why then should the RCC believers compare the Galilean miracle at Cana with their appetite for alcohol?

Further, another informant said “there was no need to stop drinking alcohol by the RCC believers since there was no verse in the Bible that prohibits alcoholism” (O.I 23/09/2019). This contradicts some Biblical texts such as Ephesians 5:18 “*Do not get drunk on wine, which leads to debauchery*”. Instead, be filled with the Spirit, which prohibits alcoholism. The current study exposes some lack of Biblical knowledge by some RCC believers. It is the moral obligation for RCC to disseminate the whole truth for their believers who may be ignorant of the misconceptions pertaining to some controversial scriptures. The findings were found to be consistent with the assertion of Kellner (2015) on the Episcopal Church.

8.2 The Teachings of Pioneer Total Abstinence Association (PTAA)

The teaching of PTAA being a minority movement of RCC on abstinence to alcohol remains the crucial link to control over alcoholism, addiction and SGA among some believers of RCC. They have a strong advocacy against all forms of alcohol which this study acknowledged. This is a pointer to the existence of varied theological, traditional and world views embraced by the RCC. Such positions point to lukewarmness to fight against alcoholism, addictions and SGA by RCC. Whereas everybody has a right to choose whether to take alcohol or not, but the existence of SGA changes the equation and the question remains, how do you segregate SGA alone in the fight against its abuse without attacking the root cause which in this case is alcohol.

Our respondent (O.I 21/09/2019) said, “PTAA has been involved in agitating for abstinence from all forms of alcohol because of its disastrous effects to the individual abuser and their families”. This shows a different radical approach to abstinence to alcohol consumption by individual believers among the RCC fraternity. It contradicts other approaches pursued by RCC such as moderation in taking alcohol, toleration of cultural orientation of congregants on alcohol and freedom of conscience and free will of an individual believer on alcohol consumption. In view of these approaches, there is contradiction that needs to be addressed.

8.3 Moderation in Alcohol Consumption Approach

The RCC support alcohol consumption in moderation and quotes Ecclesiastes 9:7 “Go, eat your bread with enjoyment and drink your wine with a merry heart for God has long ago approved what you do” (Jessie, 2018). This was also corroborated by our key informant (O.I 15/9/2019) who said, “wine should be enjoyed within the parameters of the Bible”. He continued to state that the Bible admonishes us “to avoid every kind of excess: the abuse of food, alcohol, tobacco, or medicine”. “Do not get drunk with wine, for that is debauchery; but be filled with the Spirit” (Romans 13:13; Galatians 5:19-21 and Ephesians 5:18). This position of moderation was also supported by an informant (O.I 15/09/2019). He observed that drinking is sin when done in excess. This study argues that moderation of alcohol, especially second generation alcohol is tricky as one of the respondents said, “every time he drinks a glass of “second generation” alcohol, he makes sure that a motor bike is on standby to rush him home before getting black out” (23/9/2019). This shows the fast effect of “second generation” alcohol on an individual which does not require moderation.

8.4 Teachings on Eucharist (Holy Communion)

The Holy Communion, which is also referred to as the Lord's Table is commonly known as the Eucharistic celebration by the RCC. It involves remembering the suffering and the death of Jesus Christ on the cross. The practice is sacred and has been observed over centuries. One of the questions that the current study sought to answer was whether the administration of Eucharist in the RCC influenced its believers to take alcohol.

There is the liturgy of the word and secondly liturgy of Eucharist. The importance of Eucharistic celebrations is by professing that, “the elements of bread and wine when prayed for by the priest turns to be body and blood of Jesus (O.I 15/09/2019). It is never taken symbolically as understood by the “Protestants” especially the Lutherans. This is the teaching of transubstantiation by RCC as opposed to consubstantiation by the Protestants (Lutherans). The Anglican church uses wine as symbolic (Cazalet, 2021). According to him, there are various types of altar wine which had been enjoyed by some priests. This is loaded with philosophical and theological interpretation which requires continuous teaching for believers and visitors to RCC in order to avoid controversies in its application. The understanding of wine is different from all other risky brands including illicit alcohol. Some alcoholic thirsty people would want to take advantage so as to defend their drinking problems. Such practices noted by Apostle Paul in 1Corinthians 11:20-22 (*When you meet together, you are not really interested in the Lord's Supper.....*)

The understanding of wine taken during the Eucharistic celebration has many interpretations especially among many people and believers. One of our respondents who is a practicing addiction counselor (O. I., 16/09/2019), holds that alcoholism is prevalent in the RCC because some priests have been victims of alcohol and have sought assistance at the Rehabilitation Centres. The informant also said that there is a relationship between Eucharistic celebration administration and alcohol uptake if not properly expounded; this was found to be inconsistent with the earlier findings of Slade (2020). The study found out that Eucharistic celebration is sacred and universally observed. However, care must be taken to clearly bring an understanding to the congregants and nothing should be left to chance in order to stop abuse against the doctrine of sacraments.

8.5 Teachings on Culture Toleration on Alcohol among the Local Congregation

The findings revealed that the Roman Catholic Church tolerates alcohol as a cultural way of life of a given community observing certain traditional rites and therefore does not condemn

alcohol in totality so long as those who drink do it responsibly (O.I. 15/9/2019). Another informant said “Although I am not educated to quote the Bible and give its interpretation, RCC understands our culture and does not restrict us in some things so long as you control what comes out” (O.I 23/09/2019; O.I 20/09/2019). RCC over many years have compromised on certain cultures of the local believers but strongly opposed certain rights of passage such as female genital mutilation among others. Of concern is the toleration of traditional alcohol brew taken by some believers having its roots in African Traditional Religion (ATR). Some RCC believers practice male circumcision which utilizes local brews as a sacred element of circumcision tools. This toleration of cultural traditional brew taken during male circumcision according to ATR is a factor that the government also faces.

8.6 Alcohol Addiction Due to Relaxed Teachings on freewill and conscience

Our informant (O. I. 24/09/2019) perceives that RCC considers alcohol consumption as a normal practice among some believers. Our informant (O.I 15/09/2019), said that “RCC respects the freewill and conscience of individuals especially to make their choices on alcohol”. The study recognizes the fundamental rights of individuals but in view of the presenting dangerous situation posed by SGA, observes that individuals should be assisted to make informed choices. Freedom of freewill and conscience is subject to many considerations such as helping the underage, some presenting mental health challenges, psychological and stresses occasioned by modern lifestyle. The youths also face even more challenges of exam related stress, peer pressure and unemployment which greatly interferes with their freewill and conscience leading to addictions, alcoholism and worse of SGA. The study found that SGA worsely impairs the freewill and conscience of their victims. This is clearly demonstrated by the unbecoming character of some alcoholics who sell their land cheaply and family food for peanuts, forcing women to provide for their families, who normally go without food, shelter and other basic needs. In this context, it is important not to trust an individual’s freewill and conscience but trust in the able counsel of the community and religious institutions to shape the freewill and conscience of individuals.

9. Conclusion

In conclusion the study found that there are some teachings and worldviews concerning licit alcohol observed by RCC which prompts challenges in the understanding of some RCC believers concerning SGA. Teachings on moderation and freewill pose challenges when one

takes SGA because of its toxic and dangerous nature. The study also found that although the teachings and practice by PTAA advocates for abstinence from all forms of alcohol, there are gaps which RCC need to address in order to fight and control alcoholism, addictions and second generation alcohol intake.

10. Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The teachings of PTAA against SGA should be embraced and taught from the pulpit in all the congregations of RCC in Uasin Gishu and Kenya in general. Abstinence remains the key to eradication of SGA.
- ii. The RCC and the National Council of Churches of Kenya need to partner in the spirit of ecumenism and come up with a common Bible-based teaching addressing SGA abuse commonly to be taught by all churches in Uasin Gishu and Kenya at large, as well as create awareness of the dangers of SGA.
- iii. In matters of policy, NACADA in conjunction with county governments should from time to time partner with religious organizations among other stakeholders to foster debating engagements and understanding on the emerging substance abuse and SGA in order to build their capacity of preparedness through national and regional conferences.

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